

Proposal: Community Cluster (CC)

NFDI4OBJECTS
Research Data Infrastructure
for the Material Remains of
Human History

Qualifikation und Open Educational Resources (OER)

Chairs: *Grimm, Gerda (Deutsches Archäologisches Institut); Klemstein, Franziska (HTWK Leipzig)*

NFDI4Objects-Bodies Involved: *Task Area 4, Task Area 6, TWG 2025.2 Community Recommendations for Long-Term Archiving*

External Connection: The Community Cluster will be linked to the “Training and Education” section of the NFDI Association. Regular active participation with contributions from the CC to OERcamp is planned. Members of the CC are also in various existing working groups on OER as a whole or on individual topics active. These include:

- OER-Metadatengruppe
- OER.net
- DLE Netzwerk des Stifterverbandes für die Deutsche Wissenschaft e.V.
- Data Literacy Center
- DINI/nestor Research Data WG
- SODa (Collections, objects, data literacy. Joint project to establish a data literacy center for scientific collections, <https://sammlungen.io>)

[Short Name of the Mailing List:] n4o_cc_oer@listserv.dfn.de

[Steering Committee Resolution:] *24.10.2026*

Topics and Objectives

Topics

The Community Cluster (CC) is an open forum for active participants in RDM qualification in the area of NFDI4Objects subjects who wish to participate in identifying and defining RDM areas of expertise and qualification profiles, specifying requirements for the creation of open teaching and (self)-learning materials (OER) for the community and discussing underlying infrastructural conditions. The CC also deals with strategies and processes for transforming existing documents into FAIR OER. Target group for the work of the CC are all qualification levels within and outside universities.

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Intended work results

The CC develops specific recommendations and guidelines that address the creation and transformation of OER, as well as the necessary technical infrastructure to resonate with the consortium results and objectives. In addition, the CC develops qualification profiles from which the skills of prospective RDM practitioners can be inferred. The CC ensures the intern integration and harmonization of content from individual Task Areas. Depending on participation, the establishment of TWGs on the following topics is planned in the following order:

1. “Infrastructure for OER”: Development of a recommendation for a distributed infrastructure for OER within NFDI4Objects. Publication as White Paper.
2. “OER Best Practice”: Development of a recommendation for the provision of OER. Publication as White Paper.
3. “Qualification Profiles”: Development of practice-oriented profiles for “RDM for object data” based on existing and adaptable RDM literacy frameworks.

Out of Scope

.The CC does not discuss or develop specific teaching materials for handouts and recommendations from Task Areas 1-5. Neither does it design or plan specific qualification measures. As well the CC is not actively involved in embedding the developed results in the curricula of universities or other institutions. The CC does not deal with overarching OER on the topic on RDM but rather the demands of the NFDI4Objects Community. The CC is not part of the helpdesk and does not respond to external inquiries.